

Study the Constitutional and Political Development in Pakistan (1947-1973): A Way Forwarded

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Abstract

Present research was carried out so as to determine the constitutional and political development in Pakistan since (1947-1973). In this regard, both historical and descriptive research was used. Qualitative research methods were utilized in present research, Based on objectives of the present exploration the 200 respondents (Social Science Division, University of Balochistan) among them 100 students and similar, 100 academic staff were selected as sample size based on in-depth interviews. Simple random sampling was used. However, the Cronbach's Alpha program was noted as .701. Analysis of variance, ANOVA (Duncan Multiple Range Test) or DMRT test was to run so as to denote the perception variations between groups in the present research. The p-value was calculated at 0.05 alpha levels. The finding revealed that non-significant was also observed in research question 1. The non-significant was observed at 0.05 levels in research question 2. A significant variation was observed in research question-3. Thus, the research question 4 was accepted at 0.05 level or $p >$ value. In view of the preceding conclusions, the following recommendation put forward. There should be a need of appreciation at the local to national level of the issues solution. Nevertheless the government of Pakistan has measured this issues but, reliable and steady follow-up should be mandatory.

Keywords: Pakistan, constitutional, political, development

Introduction

New protectorate of Pakistan (as the Islamic Republic of Pakistan), under the sound leadership of Muhammad Ali Jinnah (first governor general of Islamic Republic of Pakistan) as emerged the independent state on 14 August 1947. Excessive mainstream of the Indians population were remained in abode with freedom, however, in the border ranges the millions of people such as Muslim, Hindu and Sikh repositioned through the freshly drawn borders. Controversially, Punjab, whereby the new border lines and management divided the Sikh areas in partial. In the waves of violence spread in the entire regions, however, Bihar and Bengal, whereby the Gandhi's command the masses to control the violence and controlled the communal tempers toward violence. In this regard, the valance temper was denoted more limited scale. At least, 500,000 individuals on both sides of new borders of three faiths (including Muslims, Sikhs and Hindus) were died during the violence. However, the rough estimates as described by the historians that death tolls were as high as 1,500,000 (Maria, 2009; and John, 2018).

Pakistan movement

The imperative aspect of the Pakistan movement based on solidarity, faith, unity and discipline. In this regard, the prominent leadership of the all Indian Muslim League were highlighted the Pakistan word and resemblance to similitude with it 'New Medina state' for the all Indian Muslims. In other words the 2nd Islamic state recognized after the Holy Prophet Muhammad's formation of an Islamic state in the Arab Peninsula and Medina. Pakistan was commonly envisioned as an Islamic ideal, a successor to the obsolete Turkish Caliphate as well as a front-runner and guardian of the whole Islamic domain (The Express Tribune, 2015; Ashraf, 2017).

According to Islamic Calendar on 27th of Ramadan in 1366 or 14 August 1947, the Pakistan received its freedom from the British Raj. On the other hand, the India gained its freedom the next day. Bengal and Punjab were split along with religious lines through the Radcliffe Commission in the 2 provinces of British India. Mountbatten is assumed to have unfair the Radcliffe Commission to inducement the line in India's goodwill (Islam, 2002; and BBC, 2007).

In this regard, the myriad majority around ten (10) million of the people travelled crossways the new declared borders. Moreover, around 2 million persons were deceased during the communal violence in the major parts of the Punjab and adjacent areas (Dawn, 2015; Basrur, 2008; Isaacs, 1975; and Brass, 2003). 0.5 Million of the Muslim women were raped and kidnapped by the Sikh and Hindu as claimed by the Pakistani administration. Likewise the Indian administration claimed that Muslims were raped and abducted 33,000 Hindu and Sikh females (Daiya, 2011; Singh et al., 2016; and Abraham, 2002).

Post-independence features

The second Constituent Assembly of Pakistan approved the Objectives Resolution (OR) in the 12 March 1949 which declared that independence over the all-inclusive cosmos belongs to Allah alone (Hussain, n.d). In period of 1956 the declaration of constitution structure directed to Pakistan asserting itself an Islamic state (the official name) with the implementation of a legislative self-governing structure of regime. The constitution distorted the Governor-General of Pakistan obsessed by as the head of state or president of Pakistan. Consequently, the first Bengali president Iskander Mirza became the president in the year of 1956. However, self-ruled system was hindered after the President Iskander Mirza and executed by army takeover and selected the Ayub Khan as an enforcer of stratocracy (Hussain, n.d).

The president Iskander Mirza was overthrown and banished by the Ayub Khan; during his presidency did not sustained the peace and internal instability due to the 2nd war fought with India in the year of 1965. The battle had exhausted the economy and resources of the countries. The economy exhibited the disaster and upheaval consequences as the results Ayub Khan exiled during the year of 1968 GNAD, (1968-1969). Resources, economics and political grievances led to political violent and tensions as the results a civil war was begin in the East Pakistan that followed to cause the third war with India. While, Pakistan's downfall in the conflict eventually led to the separation of Bangladesh as the independent state in East Pakistan. Mr. Zulfikar Ali Bhutto from Pakistan People's Party (PPP) came into power in the year of 1972.

In this regard, he propagated the first constitution in the Pakistani parliament in the year of 1973 and declared that no Pakistani law could contradict the Islamic laws (Iqbal, 2009). Zulfikar Ali Bhutto confronted dynamic resistance from oppositions within term of (Rule of the Prophet) and opposition parties were demanded that Pakistani laws converted with the Islamic law. Zulfikar Ali Bhutto was captive by the bloodless revolution of General Zia-ul-Haq in the year of 1977 (Nasr and Nasr, 1996; and Kepel, 2002).

Zia-ul-Haq deceased by the plane crash in 1988. In this regard, the new general elections was conducted with the dawn of victory of Benazir Bhutto (PPP) and afterward she had taken the oath as the first female Prime Minister of the country. Over the following span, she staggered control and authority with Mian Nawaz Sharif who had led the traditional party like PML (N) or Pakistan Muslim League. In this period the financial condition and political scenario were worsened and weakened. Due to the military strains, conflict and war in the Kargil with India, the Mian Nawaz Sharif government was topple and overthrown by the general Pervez Musharraf and controlled the all executive powers with them in the 1999.

Early Problems as faced by the Pakistani administration

The emergence of Pakistan as the independent state, after an extensive efforts, straggle and laborious liberty drive, was actually an excessive triumph of the self-governing clue of lifespan. In this regard, myriad scarifies by the Indian Muslims to lay down their families, properties even lives so as to achieve their endpoint as target (Muslim independent state) from the Hindu and British dominance in which they lived according to their customs, mores, religion, independent life free tradition and so forth. In this regard, on 15th August, 1947, the Quaid-e-Azam inquired "my thoughts are those valiant fighters in our cause who readily sacrificed all they had, including their lives to make Pakistan possible".

From its very inception from the Hindu and British dominance, the Pakistani as the united nation were confronted a great number of difficulties. In this aspects, some of the early problems were mention below:

Establishment of government capital options

At the inception stage, the Pakistan administration had to face to choose a reasonable capital and assets as resources form, to establish a civil secretariat. In this connection, the Karachi areas was the selected as the capital city of the new-born state. However, the Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah selected the first governor general of the Pakistan, and the other hand, the Khan Liaquat Ali Khan was appointed as the first prime minister of the new-born state (Pakistan) however, in this context, senior and experienced personnel were selected for the cabinet.

Imbalanced boundary bifurcation

In order to resolve the boundary bifurcation and distribution, a boundary commission headed by the Sir Cyril Redcliff from British administration was set up. Sir Cyril Redcliff from British administration taken the biased steps and prejudiced action against Muslims as well as one-sided used his authorities. Due to the Sir Cyril Redcliff biased decision the Muslims majority region and areas like Junagadh, Ferozpur and Gurdaspur handed over India dominancy. Then Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah called this action as the injustice decision for the all India Muslims.

Distribution of military and financial Assets

The British Raj did not distributed the military and financial assets at proper manner. However, on the other hand, Pakistan administration had expressed their reservations about imbalance distribution of military empowerment and financial assets. In this regard, the India allotted the bulky financial benefits as compared to Pakistan by the British Raj. Pakistan administration was undertaken to acquire Rs. 750 million but India but unfortunately the India rejected to give the Rs. 750 million. In this regard, the Pakistani administration just received insufficient amount i.e. 200 million. Likewise the Pakistani administration also did not obtain to receive the due segment of the military resources. The biased direction towards Pakistani administration, put the country into countless problems.

Kashmir Dispute

One of the most controversial political and regional issue of the world. Still Kashmir dispute is the greatest significant and unresolved problem not only between two nationals but also worldwide dimension. Kashmir portion was considered as the natural part of Pakistan due to the facts, in the period of 1947, 85% of the Kashmir's population were belong the Muslim families. The organized conspiracy against the Kashmiri people were begin when the Dogra Rule who belong the Hindu family collaborate with Indian administration secretly and declared Kashmir as a fragment of India. However, the Pakistani administration has unceasingly claimed that Kashmir must acquire their privilege of autonomy nonetheless owing to non-cooperation of India administration, the Kashmir matter quiet remain unsolved.

Constitutional problem

Since its inception, the Pakistan have not any constitution direction until 1973. The constituent assembly unsuccessful to edge or structure to developed a constitution even in 8 years. Nonexistence of a perpetual constitution produced to chances of unprincipled meddling in self-governing development of Pakistan.

Economic problem

When Pakistan geographical position was depicted to emerge the world map as the Islamic republic of Pakistan, it typically contained of undesirable financial condition, fragile economic composition, backward, poorer physical infrastructure and underdeveloped areas. At that time the agriculture and livestock sector and system were ultimately outmoded and nonoperational. As a results the deprived economic circumstances and backwardness most of the areas in Pakistan prevailed. It was worthwhile mention that before partition of sub-continent, the Sikh and Hindus having the prevailed and special rights, and most of the British tendency and blessings towards these two communities. In addition, the British administration, had provided the altogether and complete domination in commerce and trade for Hindus. The whole wealth, money, investment, resources, funds and capital were in the hands of the Hindus communities. However, awkwardly the financial institutions and banks other development sectors were mostly situated in Indian region. The foremost industries, tanneries, business center, manufacturing factories were also remained in those location that were part of India. More interestingly most of the technical labor, manual workers, and labor forces who functioned the activities, were Sikhs and Hindus. However, the Muslims communities enormously lagged behind in professional skill, health sector, education and financial abilities. In this regard, the insufficient coordination of transportation as well as communication also made its opposing consequence on financial growth of country.

Administrative problems

Pakistan originated into being underneath the most dreadful circumstances. The Pakistani administration could not acquire sufficient period and stage to set up practical managerial mechanism owing to the prodigious problems shaped by congress in India. The Indian administration finally implemented the suspending strategies so as to shifting the government employers and official record which serious the situation. Consequently the instant mission and target beforehand the nation was to begin a practical managerial mechanism so as to run the affairs of the newly instinctive

state. Administrative and managerial bottlenecks within term of severe scarcity of capable and knowledgeable personnel was encountered by Pakistani administration specifically, in provincial and central governments. In this regard, the Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah paid the consideration en route for administrative machinery setup and took a large quantity of development steps so as to controlled the managerial glitches of the new born state.

Constitutional delinquent

At the period of foundation of Pakistan the administration of India Act 1935 turned into the working constitution of Pakistan with specific adaptations.

Electricity delinquent

Because of exchange of Muslim greater part zones to India and unfair demarcation, electricity power arrangement of West Punjab was disturbed, on the grounds that all power stations were at Mundi, a transcendently Muslim dominant part region.

Refugee's problem

In a while after freedom, Pakistan had to deal with a huge immigrant delinquent. In this regard, 5.3 million Hindus were escaped from Sindh and Punjab and into India, whereas 5.9 million Muslims were escaped from India into Pakistan. Similar, 3.3 million Hindus absconded Bengal into India, and 1.3 million Muslims population were also escaped from India into east Bengal.

Core themes

Pakistan appeared as a free Muslim state in very ominous conditions. It had no assets, it needed to develop its managerial hardware from a scratch. Be that as it may, Supreme endeavors were made by the Quaid-e-Azam and his associates to think about the circumstance. His brilliant standards Unity, Faith and Discipline offered approach to Pakistan for a splendid fate of a solid and all around created nation.

Significance of the study

Present research study was provide the valuable information regarding the constitutional and political development of Pakistan (1947-1973) for the policy maker and legislators. In this regard, the outcome of the present research was useful to the all the concern related to the developing strategies about political development of Pakistan since, 1947-1973.

Objectives

1. To understand the various constitutional and political crises in Pakistan.
2. To explore the root causes of historical political instability in Pakistan and its consequences.

Research questions

Subsequent research questions of the present research were given below.

1. Why Constitution framing process was late after independence?
2. Why were the constitutions abrogated in Pakistan?
3. What were the major political issues in Pakistan?
4. How different remedies can strengthen the system of government?

Research method

Both historical and descriptive research were carried out in the present exploration. Qualitative research methods were utilized in present research, which was predominantly supported by the historical research. University of Balochistan (Social Science Division) were selected for site. Based on objectives of the present exploration the 200 respondents

(Social Science Division, University of Balochistan) among them 100 students and similar, 100 academic staff were selected as sample size based on in-depth interviews. The descriptive research type of research survey along with qualitative study was nested, by using the simple random sampling so as to record the respondent's perceptions snapshot regarding variables. In order to determine the constitutional and political development in Pakistan from 1947 to 1973, the two hundred (200) respondents were selected by using the random sampling. However, the Cronbach's Alpha program was used so as to test the reliability. In this connection the reliability was .701, quite reliable as good. The secondary were gathered in Internet sources, indigenous and international research, journals and relevant books. The data were consistently labeling and each variables entry, coded and analysis. Analysis of variance, ANOVA (Duncan Multiple Range Test) or DMRT test was to run so as to denote the perception variations between groups in the present research. The p-value was calculated at 0.05 alpha level.

Results

The domineering feature of the present research was to determine the constitution framing process as shown in table-1.

Table, 1. Comparison score about constitution framing process

Research Question-1	Academic staff		Students		Mean Square	f-value	Si**
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D			
	3.41	.965	3.75	.744			

Note: ** = Significant at .01 level. * = Significant at .05 level.

In this regard, the research question was developed that “why constitution framing process was late after independence?”. The Likert scaling ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree was used. The alpha level was setup at 0.05 level. The non-significant was observed at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research question 1 was precluded based on perceived perception of the respondents.

Table, 2. Comparison score about constitutions abrogated in Pakistan

Research Question-2	Academic staff		Students		Mean Square	f-value	Si**
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D			
	2.62	1.229	2.92	.992			

Note: ** = Significant at .01 level. * = Significant at .05 level.

The analysis of variance (DMRT) test was used for data analysis in order that to estimate the perception value variations of research question. In this regard, the research question was developed that “why were the constitutions abrogated in Pakistan?”. At that time the alpha level was set based on ANOVA test so as to detect the liberal way of perceptions outlook. The non-significant was observed at 0.05 level. Hence, the research question 2 was irrelevant based on perceived perception of the respondents while data collection process.

Table, 3. Comparison score about major political issues in Pakistan

Research Question-3	Academic staff		Students		Mean Square	f-value	Si**
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D			
	1.93	.832	2.82	1.234			

Note: ** = Significant at .01 level. * = Significant at .05 level.

When the research was asked the question about the political issues in Pakistan shown in table-3. In this aspect, the research question was formulated. The results shown that significant variation was found in the research question 3 that “what were the major political issues in Pakistan?”. As a result, the research question 3 was accepted. And it was concluded that significant variation was observed.

Table, 4. Comparison score about different measure to strengthen the system

Research Question-4	Academic staff		Students		Mean Square	f-value	Si**
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D			
	3.28	1.083	3.79	820			

Note: ** = Significant at .01 level. * = Significant at .05 level.

Results of the table-7, revealed that significant variation between two groups was observed at 0.05 level. The highly variation was observed. The research question 4 that “how different remedies can strengthen the system of

government?" was inquired in order to recognize the perception discrepancies. Thus, the research question 4 was accepted at 0.05 level or $p >$ value.

Conclusion

The emergence of Pakistan as the independent country in the world map was the historical movement for the all Indian Muslim. Due to the effective struggle and effort of the Indian Muslim leaders as effective manner the sub-continent was divided. In the British era, the Muslims condition was miserable and considered as the ignorable object. All privileges and special rights were conferred for the Hindus and other nations by the British Raj. In this regard, the British administration were familiarized to measure the policies for the selected special individuals or elite strata. In this movement, the Muslims of sub-continent successfully achieved separate home through active efforts. The Pakistan Movement was the example of those efforts. After the independent from the British Raj the prime most obstacles were the political and constitutional development in country. Particular, the rural development and sustainable packages like (BDS) and other programs were initiated so that to improve the socio-economic condition of the rural masses. In this era saw the action against politicians (EBDO), action against Government servants (PODO), development of physical infrastructure, land reform 1959, constitutional development in 1962, presidential elections 1965 and so forth, Separation of East Pakistan 1971, has the dilemma for the political history of the Pakistan. First general election of 1970s and the most painful event of separation of East Pakistan in 1971 and the birth of Bangladesh. The safety threats, financial constraints, radical incompetency, lack of unity as the common phenomena that were existed at nationwide. The working pattern of bureaucracy, judiciary government sectors and the public politics features are halt dynamics due to the dishonesty and corruption. Somewhat, better improvement was noted in the era of Z. A. Bhutto, specially the constitution development, privatization or nationalization of basic industries, better economic reforms, superior land reforms etc.

Recommendations

In view of the preceding conclusions, the following recommendation put forward. There should be a need of appreciation at the local to national level of the issues solution. Nevertheless the government of Pakistan has measured this issues but, reliable and steady follow-up should be mandatory. Awareness sequencers as programs regarding the sustainability parameters should be steered for the masses (for their capacity building on politics) in order to promote the Pakistani motto, national harmony and play an effective role as leader in political dominoes.

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